

The Relative Stereochemistry of the Secamines, the Presecamines and their Synthetic Analogues.

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THE genus *Rhazya* of the Apocynaceae family consists of only two known species:—*Rhazya stricta*

Decaisne, a small erect shrub indigenous to north west India and *Rhazya orientalis* ADC, a plant native to north west Turkey and western Thrace. The presence of alkaloids in *R. stricta* was first detected by Hooper¹ and by 1945 its rich alkaloid content was established². In 1961 the first in a series of publications of a serious study of these alkaloids by Chatterjee and co-workers³ appeared, which reported the isolation of four crystalline bases Rhazin⁸ (Akuammidine), Rhazinine (Antirrhine), Rhazidine and Quebrachamine. *R. orientalis* was first investigated in 1964 by Joule *et al.*⁴ who identified picralinal, picrinine, vallesiachotamine and tetrahydrosecamine. Since then a number of groups have examined the constituents of these plants and the total number of indole alkaloids isolated from *Rhazya* species is now in excess of fifty. Most of this work was summarised in 1974 by Chatterjee and co-workers⁵.

The investigations of *Rhazya* species carried out in our laboratories led to the isolation of a number of interesting new alkaloids of both novel structure and biogenetic significance. Of particular importance was the discovery of the new class of bis-indolic alkaloids, the Secamines⁶ (3), since they are dimers of the dihydroderivative of secodine (1) which is postulated as a key intermediate in the indole alkaloid rearrangements from the *Corynanthe* to the *Aspidosperma* and *Iboga* classes (Fig. 1). Subsequently the closely related Presecamine (2) group were isolated⁷ and also dimers of the monomeric secodine class, itself isolated from *R. orientalis*⁸ and *Tabernaemontana cumminsi*⁹.

The chemical and spectroscopic evidence presented in the preliminary communications favoured⁷ the assignment of the gross structures 2 and 3 to presecamine and secamine respectively. Further work involving both chemical degradation and the synthesis and study of the analogous 2 and 3 ($R = \text{CH}_3$ and $R = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NMe}_2$) fully confirmed these structures. However no definitive evidence was obtained which would allow the unambiguous assignment of the detailed stereochemistry of these dimers, despite the fact that in each series both pairs of geometric isomers were available¹⁰.

Each diastereoisomer was clearly distinguishable by both chromatographic and spectroscopic analysis. The n.m.r. spectra in particular afforded characteristic signals, notably the τ -values for the methoxycarbonyl groups, which in one diastereoisomer are close together, henceforth referred to as the "narrow" diastereoisomer, and in the other further apart, the "wide" diastereoisomer. These signals, although useful in chemical equilibration studies, could not be convincingly interpreted in relation to their stereochemistry. The presecamine isomers could be interconverted by allowing the thermally produced monomer to redimerise. This Diels-Alder reaction always gave a mixture of the two presecamines containing mainly the "wide" diastereoisomer. Acid catalysed rearrangement of either presecamine isomer gave the same mixture containing mainly the "narrow" secamine, whereas methoxide catalysed equilibration of the individual secamines afforded a mixture in which the "wide" diastereoisomer predominated. Essentially the same results were obtained with the corresponding dihydro and tetrahydro-derivatives, either of natural or of semi-synthetic origin. In all

Fig. 1

Note: For the sake of simplicity and convenience, we retain the biogenetic numbering of Secodine in the synthetic skatolyl and dimethylaminoethyl presecamines and secamines.

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cases the diastereoisomers could be clearly classified according to their chemical, spectroscopic and chromatographic properties but their stereochemical identity could not be deduced from the available data.

The limited amounts of these natural products that could be conveniently prepared, together with their stereochemical complexity prompted a synthetic approach to the solution of this stereochemical problem. Accordingly the analogues in which the ethylpiperidine side chain was replaced by a dimethylamino ethyl substituent (4) or the entire side chain exchanged for a methyl group to give the corresponding skatolyl derivatives were synthesised¹⁰.

Detailed examination of the properties of these synthetic products showed a satisfactory parallel with

the natural alkaloids and the characteristic features of their chemical, spectroscopic and chromatographic behaviour are summarised in Table 1. However, although the accumulated data could be used in order to tentatively assign the configurations at the required centres¹⁰, the argument was largely based on n.m.r. interpretations which were not altogether convincing. Hence in order to provide unambiguous evidence which would finally resolve the stereochemical problems, the chemical correlations described in this paper were carried out. It is noteworthy that just as the initial discovery of these interesting dimers followed from the application of the then new technique—mass spectrometry—to the analysis of the non-crystalline alkaloids,⁸ so the final solution to their complete stereochemistry had to await the development of high performance liquid chromatography before success could be achieved.**

TABLE 1

	Tetrahydropresecamines		Dimethylaminoethylpresecamines				Skatolylpresecamines			
	"Major" Natural	"Minor"	"Major"	"Minor"	"Major"	"Minor"	"Major"	"Minor"		
Relative amounts formed in dimerisation of "acrylate"	82%	18%	70%	30%	70%	30%	70%	30%		
Ester methyls [†]	6.24, 6.44	6.21, 6.31	6.24, 6.44	6.20, 6.29	6.24, 6.43	6.16, 6.34				
Aromatic region [†]	2.2-3.8		2.3-3.8		2.2-3.3		2.2-3.6			
UV absorption	nm	log ε	nm	log ε	nm	log ε	nm	log ε	nm	log ε
	287	4.04	288	4.13	287	4.06	288	4.12	288	4.23
	293	4.12	294	4.17	293	4.12	294	4.16	294	4.30
	327	4.16	332	4.12	326	4.15	332	4.12	325	4.35
	327.5		4.23		4.28		4.23			
	Tetrahydrosecamines		Dimethylaminoethylsecamines				Skatolylsecamines			
	"Narrow"	"Wide"	"Narrow"	"Wide"	"Narrow"	"Wide"	"Narrow"	"Wide"		
Relative amounts formed in acid rearrangement	>95%	<5%	95-98%	2-5%	60%	40%				
Relative amounts in NaOMe equilbn	<5%	>95%	7%	93%	25%	75%				
Ester CH ₃ [†]	6.25, 6.28	6.24, 6.37	6.23, 6.27	6.23, 6.37	6.24, 6.29	6.28, 6.38				

* Note that no crystalline derivative of any of the presecamines or secamines has been reported yet, hence an X-ray structure determination has not been possible in this group of alkaloids.

**Recent extensive work using h.p.l.c. and the work on the skatolyl presecamine autoxidation products was carried out by G.N.S.

† NMR[†] in τ

The relative stereochemistry of the secamines

The two diastereoisomeric secamines **3** differ by the *cis* and *trans* arrangement of the two ester functions in a six-membered ring and may, in principle, be chemically distinguished by the ability of the former isomer to generate a cyclic system involving these ester functions. The simplest approach to such differentiation appeared to be the formation of a cyclic anhydride. However saponification of the skatolyl secamines to their respective dicarboxylic acids was complicated by C-16 epimerisation leading to diastereoisomeric mixtures. Since the action of acetic anhydride on these mixed dicarboxylic acids gave a further complex mixture of products, this approach had to be abandoned.

Reduction of the ester functions to their corresponding primary alcohols would preclude problems associated with base-catalysed C-16-isomerisation and a differentiation based on the secamine diols seemed attractive. Accordingly a mixture of diastereoisomeric tetrahydrosecamines was reduced with LiAlH_4 . The reaction was essentially free from C-16 epimerisation and produced the corresponding diols in high yield. The tetrahydrosecamine diols (**5**) are relatively stable to neutral or basic conditions, but unfortunately under acidic conditions dehydration occurs with surprising ease. Thus an attempt to produce a nine-membered cyclic acetal with formaldehyde led to the formation of the same elimination product (**6**) from both the *cis* and the *trans* tetrahydrosecamine diols (**5**).

The secamine diols proved to be much more convenient to handle than their ester precursors. Consequently, the skatolyl secamine diols were selected for further investigation and, since acidic conditions had

to be avoided, cyclisations of the $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ type were explored. Inspection of models revealed that the *cis* skatolyl diol (**7**) can readily form the cyclic ether (**9**) whereas the *trans* skatolyl diol (**8**) can undergo the alternative cyclisation leading to the elimination product (**10**) via N-alkylation. To test such cyclisations, the more accessible C-22 primary alcohol function must be converted into a good leaving group and thus the formation of the appropriate monotosylates was attempted.

The skatolyl secamines were each cleanly reduced with LiAlH_4 to their corresponding diols, (**7**) and (**8**) which were then subjected to tosylation under controlled conditions. These tosylation reactions were monitored by h.p.l.c. (Fig. 2), which revealed a marked difference in reactivity between the skatolyl diols. One diol, which in the event turned out to be the *cis* isomer (**7**), gave the two monotosylates (**11**) and (**13**) which were readily converted into the ditosylate (**15**). In contrast, the *trans* diol (**8**) produced the C-22-monotosylate (**12**) accompanied by only small amounts of the isomeric C-22' monotosylate (**14**) and was only slowly converted into the ditosylate (**16**). Attempts to rationalise this reactivity difference in terms of steric hindrance by a study of space-filling Stuart-Briegleb models did not succeed.

Fig. 2. Hplc chromatograms of (a) *trans* and (b) *cis* skatolyl secamine diol tosylation.

Column:— 100 × 4mm, 5 μ TMS-Spheresorb; Mobile phase:— 60% MeOHaq containing 0.1% NH_4OAc , 1 ml/min, 950 psi; Injection:— 1 μ l (variable loop); Detectors:— 254nm, Altex 153, 290nm, Perkin-Elmer LC55.

The detailed study of the tosylation of these two diols was really only made possible by frequent and rapid, quantitatively reliable h.p.l.c. analyses performed directly on aliquots taken from the total reaction

mixture. Since these analyses could be performed on the nanogram scale, the whole study consumed milligram quantities of the diols. Furthermore, it must be noted that these tosylates proved to be extremely difficult to handle and characterise other than by reversed-phase h.p.l.c. More conventional methods, i.e. t.l.c., use of separating funnels, etc. led to extensive decomposition through solvolysis and autoxidation.

Attempted cyclisations of either C-22 monotosylate (11) or (12) by base catalysis (NaH/HMPT , $\text{Bu}_4\text{NOH}^+\text{DMF}$ or MeO^-/MeOH) invariably gave very disappointing results. Although the reaction products were not fully characterised, there was no doubt that the major reaction involved elimination to the exocyclic olefin (17) which isomerised under the reaction conditions to the endocyclic isomer (18). These products were readily detected in the h.p.l.c. analyses using dual wavelength monitoring by virtue of the u.v. absorption maxima in the 310 nm region.

Similarly, the diatoylates (15) and (16) underwent base catalysed elimination to give a variety of products possessing vinyl-indole chromophores.

The isomeric C-22' monotosylates (13) and (14) do not possess a β -hydrogen and therefore cannot suffer such elimination. Unfortunately, only one of these isomers was available from the partial tosylation reactions. Treatment of this C-22' monotosylate (13) with NaH in hexamethylphosphoramide gave, in high yield, an indolic product with the expected properties of the desired ether (9). The mass spectrum of this product (Fig. 4) fully supported the assigned structure. The fragmentation pattern was unique in that a strong molecular ion at m/e 356 was accompanied by an ion m/e 311 corresponding to loss of the CH_2OCH_2 bridge together with a hydrogen atom. No fragmentation involving loss of CH_2OH (M-31) was observed as would be expected if either primary alcohol function were free.

Since it is difficult to see how under the basic conditions of tosylation and of cyclisation the stereochemistry at C-16 or C-16' could be affected, the formation of the cyclic ether (9) constitutes firm proof of the *cis* relationship of the participating functional groups from this particular diol (7). In order to fully substantiate this conclusion, a study of the action of NaH in HMPT on the C-22' monotosylate (14) from the *trans* diol (8), seemed to us to be desirable. Since direct tosylation was unsatisfactory for the production of this monotosylate (14), an indirect route had to be used. Tosylation of the C-22 monoacetate, followed by selective hydrolysis of the acetyl group under mild alkaline conditions seemed appropriate. This of course necessitated a prior study of the behaviour of the acetates of these diols, again with the aid of h.p.l.c. to optimise the reaction conditions.

The acetylation of the skatolyl diols occurred more rapidly and less selectively than their tosylation. Although the required C-22-monoacetates could be

obtained by partial acetylation, they were more efficiently prepared by selective hydrolysis of the diacetates. The C-22' acetyl group could be cleanly removed by transesterification with a methanol triethylamine reagent. The selective removal of the more hindered ester is remarkable and can be attributed to neighbouring group participation involving the indolic anion. Acid catalysed transesterification in contrast, selectively removed the C-22 acetate and significantly led to conversion of the *cis*-isomers into their thermodynamically more stable *trans* epimers (presumably by reversible C-7 protonation followed by C-16 deprotonation).

The monoacetates (19, 20, 21 and 22) and the diacetates (23 and 24) of the *cis* and *trans* skatolyl series were each clearly separable chromatographically, although the diastereoisomers gave essentially identical mass and u. v. spectra. A notable feature of the mass spectra was the favoured cleavage of the C-16'-C-22' bond which facilitated the structural assignments.

The required C-22 monoacetates (19) and (20) were converted into their tosylates (25) and (26) using excess tosyl chloride and again it was notable that the *trans* isomer was the more reluctant to react. The acetyl protecting group was cleanly removed by brief treatment with methoxide and reacylation confirmed that no other reaction had occurred. Although this acetate group could be selectively removed by acid catalysed methanolysis, in the *trans* series this reagent effected C-16 epimerisation of the *cis* isomers. The C-22' monotosylates (13) and (14) prepared by this indirect route proved to be identical chromatographically and spectroscopically with the minor monotosylates obtained by direct partial tosylation of their respective skatolyl diols.

The *trans* C-22' monotosylate (14) was now subjected to NaH/HMPT treatment and the reaction monitored by h.p.l.c. (Fig 3). Surprisingly, the tosyl group was rapidly eliminated to give a stable indolic product, to which on available evidence we assign the strained structure (28), in high yield (cf Ref. 11). Mass spectra (Fig. 4) indicated that the reaction only involved loss of toluene sulphonic acid and more importantly that the C-22 primary alcohol group was still present (M-31). This was confirmed by ready formation of the monoacetate (30) and the methyl ether (32) which resisted acetylation. The mass spectra of these derivatives paralleled that of their precursor except for the appropriate shift in the molecular ion of 42 and 14 a.m.u. respectively.

In view of these results, the behaviour of *cis* C-22'-monotosylate (13) towards NaH/HMPT was reinvestigated. Careful h.p.l.c. analysis (Fig. 3) revealed that the reaction was more complex than originally suspected. Again a rapid reaction occurred with smooth elimination of the tosyl group but, in sharp contrast to the *trans* series, the initially formed product (27, the diastereoisomer of 28) was now converted more slowly into a second product which had already been

Fig. 3. Hplc monitoring of NaH/HMPT reactions on skatolyl secamine monotosylates, (14) and (13). (a) NaH/HMPT on (14) after 2 min; (b) after 10, 90 and 120 min; (c) addition of MeI to (b) after 10 min; and (d) 20 min later. NaH/HMPT on (13) after (e) 2, (f) 20, (g) 90 and (h) 120 min. Column :- 300 x 4mm, 10 μ ODS (Waters); Mobile phase :- 75% MeCNaq., 2 ml/min, 600 psi; Injection :- 5 μ l (variable loop); Detector :- LC55 (Perkin-Elmer), 290 nm, 0.04 OD fsd.

Fig. 4. Mass Spectra of skatolyl secamine monotosylate elimination products formed by (I) NaH/HMPT or (II) NaH/HMPT/MeI treatment.

naturally occurring "narrow" secamine

assigned the desired cyclic ether structure (9). Either product could be obtained in high yield according to when the reaction was terminated. The first product (27) gave a mass spectrum (Fig. 4) practically identical with that obtained from the corresponding product (28) in the *trans* series, and furthermore, also formed a monoacetate (29) and a monomethyl ether (31). In contrast, the slowly formed product (9) gave a completely different mass spectrum (Fig. 4), failed to react with acetic anhydride in pyridine but could be methylated on treatment with NaH/HMPT followed by methyl iodide. Qualitative UV absorption spectra obtained from these cyclisation products and their derivatives were valuable in excluding several possible alternate structural assignments and representative spectra are shown in Fig. 5.

It then follows from the above work that the thermodynamically more stable "wide" skatolyl secamine can be assigned the *trans* structure (44) and that thermodynamically less stable "narrow" isomer, that which is kinetically favoured in the presecamine rearrangement, can be assigned the *cis* structure (42).

Since, as can be seen from Table I, there is an obvious correlation on the one hand between the "narrow" skatolyl-, dimethylaminoethyl- and natural-

Fig. 5. Qualitative UV absorption spectra of skatolyl secamine monotosylation products formed by (1) NaH/HMPT or (2) NaH/HMPT/MeI treatment.

secamines, and on the other hand between the corresponding "wide" isomers, the thermodynamically less stable "narrow" secamine can with confidence be assigned the *cis* structure (46). We would like to emphasise the fact that all the work on the skatolyl secamine diols we have just described was carried out on about 20 mg of the "major" and about 15 mg of the "minor" skatolyl presecamines. Most of the material was lost in the exploration of the various tosyl derivatives before it was realised that these compounds do not survive t.l.c. and the more conventional work-up procedures. In the end, all separations were carried out by h.p.l.c. By the time the reactions were being carried out on the microgram scale, and essentially only mass and qualitative UV spectra, together with chemical logic and chromatographic data could be used to make the structural assignments.

The above stereochemical conclusions and the structures of many of the compounds described must therefore be regarded to be subject to confirmation by further work on a larger scale, which will allow proper NMR and quantitative UV data to be obtained.

We have in fact a number of 300 MHz ^1H NMR spectra, measured on 50 to 100 microgram quantities: whilst these very weak spectra on the whole support our structural assignments, there are some features which at the moment cannot be properly interpreted: these may be due to trace impurities, to the presence of rotamers, etc., or it is just possible that they may require some of our conclusions to be revised.

The relative stereochemistry of the presecamines

Dimerisation of dihydrosecodine (1) affords two diastereoisomeric presecamines (2) which differ accord-

ing to whether the quaternary side-chain and the ester function are in a *cis* or *trans* relationship. Since the dimethylamino- and skatolyl presecamines are obligatory intermediates in the synthesis of the corresponding secamines, they have been studied in detail¹⁰. However, despite the availability of each diastereoisomer in all three series, and the accumulation of an impressive amount of spectroscopic data, summarised in Table 1, tentative stereochemical conclusions¹⁰ based mainly on NMR data remained unconvincing.

Whilst this relative stereochemistry of the C-7' and C-16 centres has not been unambiguously solved, a reinterpretation of previous data combined with recent results has led us to favour structure (37) for the 'major' presecamine isomer.

Reinvestigation of the skatolyl presecamines (36) and (37) revealed that although extensive autoxidation had occurred on prolonged storage, the minor presecamine (36) had been mainly converted into a more polar product (38) whilst the major presecamine (37) afforded the related isomer (39). The same products could be obtained by simply refluxing the corresponding presecamine in dioxan in the presence of air. This remarkably clean reaction occurred stereospecifically since only one diastereoisomer was detected by t.l.c. or h.p.l.c. Notably the minor skatolyl presecamine (36) was the more susceptible to autoxidation.

The gross structure of these oxidation products was deduced largely from their UV absorption, which corresponds to the summation of an indole and a

Fig. 6. Mass spectra of autoxidation products (38) and (39) formed from the (a) major or (b) minor skatolyl presecamines.

simple 3H indole system, and from their mass spectra (Fig. 6) which possess a molecular ion, $C_{28}H_{28}N_2O_5$, in accord with the introduction of a single oxygen atom. Thus, the products were suspected to be the hydroxy-3H-indoles (38) and (39) formed by oxidative attack at C-16 of the β -anilino-acrylate system of the presecamines.

This conclusion was substantiated by the ready acid-catalysed rearrangement of either oxidation product (38) or (39) to the same crystalline, unsaturated skatolyl secamine (40) whose structure was unambiguously assigned by a full spectroscopic study (IR, UV, NMR and MS).

An inspection of Stuart-Briegleb models shows that in both skatolyl presecamines, (36) and (37), the side on which the angular methyl stands (the α -face of the structures as drawn) offers considerably less hindrance to attack at C-16. Given that the autoxidation appears to be stereoselective, then it seems to us quite reasonable to assume that attack by peroxide or by singlet oxygen will occur preferentially at the less hindered side. The proposed relative stereochemistry of the oxidation products, (38) and (39) rests on this argument. Since the stereochemical relationship at the C-7 and C-16' centres is unaffected by the oxidation process, the structure of the autoxidation products forms the main evidence for the assignment of the relative stereochemistry of the presecamine also.

A differentiation between the two most probable structures for the hydroxy-3H-indole derived from the two skatolyl presecamines, (36) and (37), emerges from a study of their mass spectra (Fig. 6). Despite the overall resemblance of these two spectra there are a number of important differences which taken in isolation are not remarkable but when considered as a whole provide complementary evidence in support of the assigned structures. The most significant difference involves the ion m/e 400 and associated metastable $m^* = 358.7$ found only in the oxidation product (38) obtained from the minor skatolyl presecamine (36). This fragmentation is compatible with the elimination of the elements of dimethyl ether (M-45) which is only feasible if the two methoxycarbonyl substituents bear a *cis* relationship to each other. This isomer (38) also undergoes dehydration (m/e 428) which is not observed for the alternative isomer (39) where an increased loss of methanol, m/e 414, is observed instead. The increased tendency for the oxidation product (39), from

the major skatolyl presecamine (37), to eliminate methanol is in accord with the *cis* relationship between the C-16' methoxycarbonyl and the C-16 α hydroxyl substituent. Although other features of these mass spectra may be rationalised in terms of the assigned structures, the increasing number of possible fragmentation pathways leading to the lower mass ions renders such speculation pointless.

Thus the fortuitous isolation of the autoxidation products of the skatolyl presecamines, together with their characteristic mass spectra has allowed the provisional stereochemical assignment of these isomers. Supporting evidence is available from a consideration of the relative stabilities of the diastereoisomeric presecamines. The 'major' presecamines are undoubtedly thermodynamically more stable than their diastereoisomers, (*vide infra*). With the assigned structures, this difference in stability can be reasonably attributed to the greater steric requirements for the indolic system as compared with the methoxycarbonyl group. Thus as the size of the β -indolic substituent increases from CH_3

to $CH_2CH_2NMe_2$ then CH_2CH_2N , so the

yield of the less stable presecamine decreases. Furthermore, there is a characteristic difference between the UV absorption spectra of the presecamine diastereoisomers. The major isomer always exhibits a greater contribution from the β -anilinoacrylate chromophore to the spectrum than is observed with the less stable diastereoisomer (see Table 1). Clearly the increased steric interaction between the C-7 substituent and the juxtapositioned bulky indolic system in the minor presecamines (36) is partly relieved at the expense of orbital overlap in the β -anilino-system. This rationalisation also accounts for the increased susceptibility of the minor presecamines towards autoxidation.

Although the preceding evidence does not completely prove the stereochemical assignments for the presecamines, it does provide a consistent case.

The presecamine-secamine interconversions

The acid-catalysed rearrangement of presecamines to secamines and the base-catalysed equilibration of the secamines had been studied in some detail in the hope that an understanding of the reaction mechanisms would enable the stereochemistry of the participating isomers to be deduced. Earlier results¹⁰, summarised in Table 1, were obtained, only after considerable effort, by UV-monitoring of the reaction, followed by preparative t.l.c. and spectroscopic analysis of the final reaction products. Such procedures were time-consuming and inevitably incurred losses of these relatively labile compounds. It is precisely in this kind of situation that h.p.l.c. can be most effectively used in order to provide quantitative information on reaction intermediates which could otherwise escape detection.

The skatolyl series turned out to be the most complicated in terms of the number of competing

reactions and has been studied in most detail. Fortunately, these neutral compounds could be readily resolved by reversed-phase h.p.l.c. and the ability to simultaneously monitor the chromatograms at two wavelengths proved invaluable. Representative chromatograms illustrating the sequence of events which occurred when the minor product of the skatolyl acrylate ester dimerisation, the skatolyl presecamine (36), was treated with 2*N* HCl in methanol are shown in Fig 7. Surprisingly, the minor skatolyl presecamine (36) was first rapidly transformed into the epimeric skatolyl presecamine (37). Then, a slower transformation to the "narrow" skatolyl secamine (42) occurred. Finally, the "wide" skatolyl secamine (44) appeared and continued to slowly accumulate until after prolonged reaction the gradual appearance of more polar hydrolysis and/or autoxidation products curtailed further worthwhile analysis.

Fig. 7. Hplc monitoring of the skatolyl presecamine-secamine interconversions. Rearrangements of the minor skatolyl presecamine (36) in 2*N* HCl/MeOH (1 : 4) at 40°; after (a) 2 min, (b) 20 min, (c) 120 min. MeO⁻/MeOH catalysed equilibration of the skatolyl secamines (38) or (39) at 22° after (d) 2 and 10 min. Column:— 100 × 4.6 mm, 5 μ TMS-Spheresorb; Injection:— 1 μl reaction mixture; Mobile phase:— 55% MeOH/aq containing 0.1% NH₄OAc, 1 ml/min, 500 psi; Detection:—254 nm, Altex 153 and 253 nm, Perkin-Elmer LC55.

With the exception of the initial epimerisation, the major skatolyl presecamine (37) showed parallel behaviour on similar acid catalysed treatment. It is noteworthy that previous studies¹⁰ of the acid-catalysed rearrangement of both natural and synthetic presecamines had established that the "minor" isomers always took longer than the major isomers to complete the rearrangement to the secamines, although at the time this observation could not be rationalised.

Either skatolyl secamine could be rapidly converted into the same equilibrium mixture of the two epimers using MeO⁻/MeOH catalysis (Fig. 7). Undoubtedly the same equilibrium would eventually have been reached by the acid treatment except for the intervention of the side-reactions. In an attempt to increase the rate of acid-catalysed equilibration each skatolyl secamine was treated with anhydrous formic acid. Rapid h.p.l.c. analysis as soon as complete solution occurred gave identical chromatograms from either isomer. Only minor changes occurred over several hours and thus equilibration had indeed been rapidly established. Remarkably, however the major component of this equilibrium (ca. 60%) was identified as skatolyl presecamine (37) by u.v., h.p.l.c. and t.l.c. comparison with authentic material. The skatolyl secamines thus rearrange back to their presecamine precursors in formic acid. This observation is in marked contrast to their natural and dimethylamino analogues where treatment with formic acid rapidly converts the presecamine derivatives to their secamine isomers.

Less detailed study of the acid catalysed rearrangement of the dimethylamino presecamines (4) by h.p.l.c. monitoring has confirmed our previous results¹⁰. The only new finding is that again the "minor" presecamine is initially converted into the "major" presecamine before any appreciable rearrangement to the "narrow" secamine occurs. Furthermore, only a small amount of the thermodynamically more stable "wide" secamine is produced on such acid treatment which does not lead to equilibration of these dimethylamino secamine derivatives. Base catalysed equilibration using MeO⁻/MeOH however effectively equilibrates these isomers leading to a preponderance of the thermodynamically more stable "wide" (*trans*) isomer.

The detailed information provided by the direct h.p.l.c. analysis of these presecamine-secamine reaction mixtures can now be rationalised in a mechanistically plausible manner. The main features are summarised in Scheme 1 for the more complex skatolyl series. On mild acid treatment C-16 protonation of the anilino-acrylate system of the minor skatolyl presecamine (36) followed by ring-opening affords the transient resonance stabilised open cation (41) which must be sufficiently long-lived to allow conformational rotatory movements before preferential reversible ring closure occurs to the thermodynamically more stable skatolyl presecamine (37). More slowly, the open cation (41) then undergoes preferential reversible C-16'-N cyclisation to the "narrow" (*cis*) skatolyl secamine, (42), which is the next kinetically most favoured molecule in this series of reversible

Scheme I
The Presecamine - Secamine interconversions in the Skatolyl series.

reactions. Conceivable reversal of this transformation followed by C-16'-N ring closure of the alternative C-16' C-17' rotamer of cation (41) could lead to the thermodynamically more stable skatolyl secamine (44). However, in view of the marked difference in the

behaviour of the skatolyl secamines, compared with their basic dimethylamino- and natural analogues, towards acid catalysed equilibration and reformation of their presecamine precursors on treatment with formic acid, it seems more probable that the skatolyl secamines are interconverted *via* the acrylate (43) formed by initial β -protonation followed by C-16 deprotonation. This route would be expected to be inhibited in the case of the basic secamines by virtue of the proximity of the positively charged side-chain nitrogen formed by preferential protonation of this basic centre. The base catalysed epimerisation of all three secamine series is an unexceptional equilibration and proceeds by way of the anion (45).

The stereochemical considerations which determine the relative rates of these reversible reactions is not at all evident to us. Detailed study of models has failed to reveal why the *cis* secamines should be the kinetically controlled product of the presecamine rearrangement or indeed why the *trans* secamine should be thermodynamically more stable.

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